

Diurnal cycle simulations of thermally stratified flows over forests

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Outline

Motivation

Coupling methodology

Description of the physical model

Diurnal cycle simulation

Conclusion and Future work

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Motivation. How to drive the diurnal cycle in forested areas?

- To impose a time dependent **ground temperature** is an ineffective methodology.
- Turbulent mixing decreases inside **forests**; **partially isolating** temperature at ground level from the wind above the forest.

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Modelling of thermally stratified flows in forested areas

- We assume a net **radiative** heat flux **decreasing** inside the canopy (Brown and Covey (1966)).

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} - \nabla \cdot (\nu_t \nabla^s \mathbf{u}) + \nabla p + f_c \mathbf{e}_z \times (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_g) + c_d A |\mathbf{u}| \mathbf{u} = -\mathbf{g} \frac{\theta}{\theta_0} \quad \text{Momentum}$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \theta - \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\nu_t}{\sigma_\theta} \nabla \theta \right) = \frac{\partial q_r}{\partial z}(z) \quad \text{Energy}$$

The net radiative flux pointing downwards q_r is distributed as

$$q_r(z, t) = \begin{cases} Q_{z_c}(t) & z > z_c \quad (\text{above the canopy}) \\ Q_{z_c}(t) \exp(-\eta \int_z^{z_c} A dz) & z \leq z_c \quad (\text{inside the canopy}) \end{cases}$$

- The prescribed **downward net radiation** just above the top of the canopy $Q_{z_c}(t)$ drives the heat transport through the ABL.
- Heat flux modelled for stable and unstable condition through opposite signs on Q_{z_c} .

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Diurnal cycle simulation at Ryningsnäs forested site

- We use a RANS k - ε single column model (based in Sogachev 2012).
- 9 days of simulation at flat **Ryningsnäs** forested site.
- Height of forest set to $z_c = 20m$, and LAI=3.
- **Net radiation** above the canopy $Q_{z_c}(t)$ obtained from field measurements.
- **Driving pressure gradient** is obtained from WRF at ground level.
- No slip velocity and constant temperature at ground level.

Measured radiative heat flux is imposed at canopy top

Turbulent heat flux at 40m and 138m agl along 9 days.

- Large differences of heat fluxes found during nights at 40 m.
- Omitting latent heat and heat storage in the canopy.

Diurnal cycle simulation

Geostrophic pressure gradient, from WRF, driving the flow

Wind Speed

Wind Direction.

- Driving pressure gradient is a **meso-micro** momentum budget **coupling**¹.

¹Sanz Rodrigo et al, Wind Energy Sci. 2017

Diurnal cycle simulation

Height of PBL.

- Large variations of height of PBL from day to night.
- Low height of PBL during 3rd and 4th nights may indicate strong nocturnal stratification.

Diurnal cycle simulation. Vertical profiles

Upward turbulent heat flux Profile

TKE Profile

- Change of heat flux direction inside the canopy.
- TKE and turbulent heat very low inside the forest.

Diurnal cycle simulation. Results vs measurements.

Velocity Profiles at different times along 4rd day

- Velocity variations mainly due to thermal stratification effects.

Diurnal cycle simulation. Results vs measurements.

Temperature profiles at different times along 4rd day

- Consequence of prescribing net radiation.
- Opposite nocturnal temperature gradient found inside the forest (Drainage currents, latent heat,?)

Diurnal cycle simulation. Time series.

Wind Speed at 40m and 138m agl

- Reasonably good agreement at lower height $z=40\text{m}$
- Underestimation of wind speed during nighttime at height 138m. Maybe because nocturnal boundary layers are modeled too shallow.

Diurnal cycle simulation. Time series.

Temperature at 40m and 138m agl

- Although temperature is held constant at ground level, temperature variation above the forest is well captured by the model.

Diurnal cycle simulation. Time series.

Turbulent Kinetic Energy at 40m and 138m agl.

- Strong variations of TKE from day- to night-time.
- TKE underestimated close to noon.

Conclusion

- **Simple coupling** prescribing net **radiative** heat flux balance at the top of the canopy, and geostrophic pressure gradient.
- Net radiation is readily **available** from meteorological reanalysis and is easy to measure.
- Reasonably good agreement against measurements assuming homogeneity. Capture of convective and stably stratified profiles.
- Wind speed is underpredicted at 138 m height specially during nights. This can be probably improved using a LES model.
- To account for latent heat can also lead to more accurate results.

Future Work

- To extend this methodology to **complex and forested terrain** (Hornamossen benchmark).
- Analyze the imposition of net radiation together with temperature at ground level in forests and clearings.
- Coupling with WRF using tendencies depending on height and time.

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Thank you!
Questions?